

USING ROUND TABLE DISCUSSIONS TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This research work is aimed at studying the state of formation of communication skills of no philological students by organizing the effective use of the method of round table discussions in English lessons, identifying positive approaches to solving it and defining the conceptual apparatus of research.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, it is important that students are not the object of passive influence, but that they can independently find the necessary information, exchange views on a particular problem, find evidence and rebuttals, and play different roles. It should be noted that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev pays special attention to the formation of communicative skills of children in foreign languages, which plays an important role in ensuring the future of our country and its development. They are the main ones who can perfectly shape the speech skills of the young generation as well. Decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev No. 4947 "On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017, radically improve the

quality of general education, facilitate in-depth study of foreign languages, computer, science and some tasks have also been mentioned to improve the teaching process of other specific sciences. Learning a foreign language in education system is a complex process of forming the ability to communicate, which already exists with the already developed system of the mother tongue and begins to interact constantly.

This research presents some methods of developing speaking skills in English lessons for students, as well as the results of experimental work on the formation of speech in the context of topics that can be used in the classroom. It analyzes the discussion technology, its types and place, based on the method of round table discussion in the formation of speaking

skills of no philological students. The scientific work is a scientific report aimed at finding answers to the following problems and questions:

1. What is the round table discussion method and what are the effective ways to use it?
2. What is the need to develop the speaking skills of no philological students?
3. What are the problems and solutions to improve speaking skills using round table discussions?

To answer these questions, the researcher examines various works on the topic and conducts experiments with students.

II. BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

Modern English teaching has also been supplemented by many new methods and techniques, such as project method, critical thinking, case method, debate, and more. now it is time to consider the advantages or disadvantages of the new methods introduced into the educational process, as well as the hard and extensive work on the methods, showing that the same method can be used differently through different approaches indicated that it should be carried out. They need to be revised, modernized and defined in an innovative education structure.

Special attention should be paid to the new roundtable method, which is the most widely used in the current period. Round table discussion is an active method of teaching, one of the organizational forms of students' cognitive activity, which allows to consolidate previously acquired knowledge, fill in missing information, form problem-solving skills, strengthen positions, teach a culture of knowledge.

This teaching method includes: various types of seminars and discussions. This method is based on the principle of

community and is used in the task of discussing the problems studied in the education system, and the existing problems are solved through a creative approach using language skills. Such methods are in giving students the opportunity to speak facilitates the practical application of theoretical knowledge in the context (Kolokolnikova2015).

Of course, student round tables are not a novelty, but the ability to present one's idea in a foreign language, to understand and comprehend the ideas of others, to evaluate or criticize someone's judgments is a skill that greatly contributes to self-development and self-organization of students.

A roundtable discussion is a place where two or more people discuss a specific topic on the agenda, a place for discussion, and a joint exchange of ideas to find a clear answer and solution. The purpose of the roundtable discussion is to give each participant an equal position in the discussion, allowing them to freely and fully contribute their views and ideas to the conversation. This type of discussion is short, usually 1 hour in the course process.

Picture 1. Round table discussion

Round Table Circles (RTC) is a method of round table discussion used to engage students in ways that helps them integrate new and interesting content knowledge with prior knowledge through a structured round table debate format.

Round table is a form of academic discussion. Participants agree on a specific topic to discuss and debate. Each person is given equal right to participate, as illustrated by the idea of a circular layout referred to in the term round table.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The research design applied in this research was Quasi-experimental which applied the non-equivalent Control Group Design with Pre-test and Post-test. Sugiyono (2014) stated that in this design, there were two groups which were taken randomly.

In order to determine the results of scientific work, experimental tests are conducted on a regular basis for a pre-selected group, as well as entrance and exit tests at the beginning and end of the quarter, as well as for other groups, which did not conduct experiments at all. "Input" and "output" tests are performed and the results are compared.

B. Participants

Roundtables are one way of approaching individual presentations that are conducted

by students and require prior preparation if necessary. Roundtables can also be organized into small groups of five students, with each participant having a role to play and each student taking on a role. These roles are shared between students throughout the lessons, allowing students to practice each role. Roles: Trainer, "Word of the Day" speaker, prompt speaker, introductory speaker and informative speaker. Each role requires a different presentation that allows students to practice different presentations. The process of changing roles each time requires a different responsibility each time.

Roles of Round table discussion		
Facilitator		
Responsible for leading the group:	Preparation:	Note:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ welcoming students to the Round Table ✓ providing introductory remarks o following the Round Table agenda ✓ monitoring time ✓ facilitating discussion after each member's speech ✓ encouraging all students to participate o tallying participation ✓ closing the Round Table by thanking everyone for their participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ making the agenda ✓ bringing a timer 	This role does not include a formal speech; instead, it focuses on practical, academic, and professional facilitation skills (e.g., leading a meeting, encouraging participation, and keeping students on task).
Word of the Day Speaker		
Responsible for teaching a new vocabulary word:	Preparation:	Notes:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ choosing a new vocabulary word to teach to the group (the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ choosing a word that will build their group's vocabulary 	Once the word of the day has been taught to the group, each member is encouraged

<p>speaker can choose an academic word, an idiom, slang, or a course-content word)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ preparing for their speech ✓ delivering a 3-minute speech teaching the new lexical item answering clarification and follow-up questions during the question and answer session tallying use of the word of the day ✓ listening for and tallying hesitation markers (umm, err, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ getting teacher approval ✓ preparing a handout explaining the word, including the definition(s) as well as one to three sample sentences ✓ practicing their speech 	<p>to use the word throughout the Round Table. The Word of the Day Speaker monitors the number of times the word is used by tallying each student's use of the word. Students often utilize their new vocabulary knowledge during the post-presentation discussion for each role, when they are asking and answering questions. There is no set limit on how many hesitation markers are acceptable in students' speech. The purpose of this is to raise students' self-awareness of the use of these markers. It can be beneficial to have students tally a teacher's hesitation markers during a sample presentation, to show students that the use of these markers is acceptable.</p>
Impromptu Speaker		
<p>Responsible for delivering an impromptu speech:</p>	<p>Preparation:</p>	<p>Notes:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ receiving a topic from the teacher ✓ spending 2 minutes to prepare a speech, taking notes and referring to a dictionary as needed ✓ delivering a 2-minute speech on the topic ✓ answering clarification and follow-up questions during the question and answer session 	<p>None</p>	<p>-</p>
Introduction Speaker		

<p>Responsible for delivering a formal speech introducing a person or thing or explaining a process:</p>	<p>Preparation:</p>	<p>Notes:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ choosing an appropriate introduction topic (some sample topics are “My Best Friend,” “My Family Trip to London”) ✓ preparing for their speech o delivering a 4-minute speech o answering clarification and follow-up questions during the question-and-answer session 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ choosing a topic ✓ getting teacher approval ✓ creating a speech outline ✓ preparing a visual aid (e.g., a PowerPoint, either on a computer or a printed copy of the slides; photos; or anything else to help explain the student’s topic) o practicing their speech 	<p>Students are encouraged to use content that they are already familiar with and to focus on improving their formal speaking abilities. Allowing students to choose this type of content lowers students’ affective filter, which encourages them to produce more complex language and limits their anxiety as they build on their presentation skills (Dörnyei, 2005). This presentation and the question-and-answer session creates authentic, meaningful discussion and promotes team building, as students are genuinely interested in the Introduction Speaker’s topic.</p>
<p>Informative Speaker</p>		
<p>Responsible for delivering a formal, academic speech:</p>	<p>Preparation:</p>	<p>Notes:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ choosing an appropriate topic (some sample topics are “Social Networking Services” and “The Importance of Water in Developing Countries”) ✓ preparing for their speech delivering a 5-minute speech teaching the group about the topic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ choosing a current and relevant topic ✓ getting teacher approval researching the topic ✓ creating a speech outline ✓ preparing a PowerPoint presentation and outline ✓ practicing their speech 	<p>This is the most formal speech in Round Tables. The content of this speech is different from that of the Introduction Speech as it is academic in nature and should be supported by research.</p>

✓ answering clarification and follow-up questions during the question-and-answer session		
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Table 1. Roles of Students in round table discussion

C. Data Collection and Analysis

The research work refers to a quantitative type of research. The analysis of the data is based on numerical method. The results of the progress tests and the final test are reported in numbers and expresses in graphs. Interval and ordinal

scales are used in order to count the results and show the difference between two groups. Moreover, the researcher intends to use both central tendency and dispersion techniques.

Students score classifications	
90-100	excellent
80-90	Very good
71-80	good
61-71	Fairly good
55-60	Not bad
40-54	poor
0-39	Very poor

Table 2. Students score classification in assessment process

The procedure of collecting data in this research as follows:

1. Pre-test

Pre-test is a test which was given before the treatment. It was given both of the experimental and controlled group class. It aims to equate the initial capabilities of two different groups.

2. Treatment

After given pre-test, the experimental class was given treatment which was applied round table techniques. Treatment is the action to overcome the problem in the class by applied method or approach.

3. Post-test

After giving the treatment, both experimental and control class were given post test. It is used to measure whether the use of round table techniques was effective to improves students' speaking ability.

IV. RESULTS

1. The Classification of Students' Pre-test and Post-test Scores in Experimental Class

The following table showed the distribution of frequency and percentage of final score of students' speaking ability of both group students in pre-test and post-test in experimental class.

No.	Scale	Classification	Pre-test		Post-test	
			Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage

1	90-100	excellent	0	0%	1	3%
2	80-90	Very good	0	0%	5	10%
3	71-80	Good	1	5%	12	40%
4	61-71	Fairly good	3	15%	11	35%
5	55-60	Not bad	7	20%	3	7%
6	40-54	poor	9	25%	2	5%
7	0-39	Very poor	14	35%	0	0%
Total			34	100%	34	100%

Table 3. Results of experimental group

The table above shows that the previous results are not very good, but it is common to see that their speaking skills have increased after using the round table discussion, and the result is significantly positive.

2. The Classification of Students' Pre-test and Post-test Scores in Controlled Class

The following table shows the distribution of frequency and percentage of final score of second semester students in pre-test and post-test in controlled class.

No.	Scale	Classification	Pre-test		Post-test	
			Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	90-100	excellent	0	0%	0	0%
2	80-90	Very good	0	0%	0	0%
3	71-80	good	0	0%	0	0%
4	61-71	Fairly good	0	0%	2	10%
5	55-60	Not bad	1	5%	2	10%
6	40-54	poor	4	20%	5	25%
7	0-39	Very poor	15	75%	11	55%
Total			20	100%	34	100%

Table 4. Results of controlled group

The given table showed that it is difficult to see a significant increase in the results of this group, in which only the input and output tests were performed without the experiment.

3. The Mean Score and Standard Deviation of Experimental Class and Controlled Class in Pre-test and Post-test

After calculating the result of the students score, the mean score and standard deviation of both classes can be presented in the following figure:

Figure 3. The mean score and standard deviation of experimental class and controlled class in pre-test

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the same results can be achieved only if the educational process is well organized and has a targeted approach. Also, since speaking skill is the key to this communication process, the old approaches used in the course process should be abandoned, and various interactive methods should be used. Then one of the interactive methods is round table discussion. Through this type of approach, speaking skills are developed while increasing students' communicative

competence. The effective results of this can also be seen in the process of scientific and financial research conducted by the researcher and its results.

The data above showed that students' mastery in experimental class was higher than in controlled class. Based on the result of the data analysis, research findings, and discussion in the previous chapter, the researcher concluded that the students' mastery on speaking increased to a greater extent through applying round table technique in the class.

References:

1. Azimov E.G., Schukin A.N. A new dictionary of methodological terms and concepts (theory and practice of teaching languages). M.: IKAR Publishing House, 2009. P. 264.
2. Decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev No. 4947 "On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017
3. Kolokolnikova Z.U. Technology of active teaching methods in vocational education. Tutorial. URL http://www.files.lib.sfukras.ru/ebibl/umkd/359/u_course.pdf (date of access: 02/27/2015)
4. Kubrakova N.A. Conducting English-speaking round tables as a means of implementing the project method. //Linguistic and methodological problems of teaching foreign languages in higher education. Interuniversity collection of scientific papers. Issue 8. Saratov, 2011.

5. Richards, J., Rodgers, Theodore. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching (3rd Edition). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. pp. 23–24, 84–85. ISBN 978-1-107-67596-4. – 2014. Pp. 23-24.
6. The Role of Teachers in Developing Speaking Skills. Academician, SAARJ Publications. 8(12), Pp. 84-96. DOI Number: 10.5958/2249-7137.2018.00068.X, www.saarj.com, 2018. Online.
7. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Round_table_\(discussion\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Round_table_(discussion))